

Effect of Medicinal Plant Gums and Other Surface Active Substances on the Particle Size Distribution of Emulsion Stabilised by Nicotine Hydrogen Tartrate

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Nicotine-hydrogen-tartrate alone is not capable of giving stable emulsions with the systems kerosene oil/water and xylene/water. Stable o/w emulsions do result with binary mixtures of nicotine-hydrogen-tartrate and gums (dhavda and salai), other adjuvants such as cetyl-trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTMAB), sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), saponin, gelatin. Lecithin can not be recommended as good emulsifying agent. The nature of internal phase plays an important role as it is evident from the globule size distribution, practically as well as graphically determined initial specific interfacial areas and stability coefficient values.

PLANT-DERIVED poisons are generally characterised by their greater safety for use on plant foliage than most inorganic compounds. The structure or form of the compounds is usually rather easily broken down into harmless bodies. The alkaloid nicotine is basic in reaction levorotatory, volatile and much more toxic in this form than when combined with acids (dextrorotatory) to form non-volatile or fixed compounds¹.

Richardson and Shepard² found that nicotine as the free base was from 5 to 7 times as toxic as nicotine sulphate or hydrochloride when tested against mosquito larvae, but Starr and Richardson³ comparing 1-nicotine d-tartrate against 1-nicotine, found the former to be slightly (possibly not significantly) more toxic than the latter.

The volatile nicotine sprays and dusts are used principally against soft bodied insects, including aphids, thrips, psyllids, tingids, poultry lice, a very few of the beetles and young lepidopterous larvae and sawflies.

Fixed or stable nicotine compounds are of permanent or residual type that is effective over a period of many days. They may be injected by feeding on coated leaves or act as a repellent to prevent feeding and induce migration. Non-volatile compounds have been used principally against codling moth (*Carpocapsa pomonella*)^{4,5,6}, grapeberry moth (*Polychrosis oitecona*), pistol case-bearer (*Coleophora malivorella*)⁷ and citrus thrips⁸.

A survey of the literature reveals that no work has been done on the emulsifying capability of nicotine-hydrogen tartrate. In continuation with the previous work on insecticides and medicinal plant gums of India

in the present work it is intended to study the effect of addition of a few Indian medicinal plant gums and other surface active substances on the particle size distribution and stability of emulsions stabilised with nicotine-hydrogen tartrate.

Experimental

The emulsions were prepared using nicotine hydrogen tartrate to contain 40% (kerosene oil or xylene) as the internal phase. Emulsions were also prepared by adding the minimum quantity of purified gum or other adjuvant to the fixed quantity of nicotine-hydrogen-tartrate in 60 c.c. of water. The suspensions were made by slightly warming at 60-80° over a water bath. Then the emulsions were made in the usual manner as described by Mukerjee and Shukla⁹.

The size frequency analyses were made immediately and at different intervals of time by the method of King and Mukerjee¹⁰. The change of specific surface was plotted against time as abscissa for several emulsions to illustrate the agreement between the data on the change of specific surface with time and exponential hypothesis. The lines were determined by fitting the data to the equation :

$$- \frac{d\sigma}{dt} = K'\sigma = \frac{\sigma}{K}$$

(where σ = specific surface, K' = instability coefficient and K = stability coefficient) by the method of *least squares*^{11,12}. The curves representing the degradation of the emulsions are all linear; hence a measure of the slope provides a quantitative comparison of stability. Accordingly, the slope of each curve has been measured and divided by the graphically determined initial interfacial (σ_0) to furnish the rate of decrease per unit area

of interface. This is termed as the instability factor and might be defined as the decrease of each cm^3 of fresh emulsion per day. The reciprocal of this would be a direct measure of emulsion stability.

Results and Discussion

Emulsions were prepared using kerosene oil and

xylene, stabilised by nicotine-hydrogen-tartrate as emulsifying agent. Different percentages of Indian medicinal plant gums and other adjuvants were also tried as emulsion stabilisers. The results are too numerous to quote in full. Only the summarised results have been given in Table 1. A few representative curves between particle diameter and percentage of particles have been depicted in Fig. 1.

TABLE 1—DATA FOR 40% KEROSENE OIL AND XYLENE EMULSIONS

Emulsion no.	Agents	KEROSENE OIL			Emulsion no.	XYLENE		
		Initial area	Specific $\times 10^{-2}$	Stability coefficient		Initial specific area $\times 10^2$	Stability coefficient	
		Experimental cm^2/gm	Graphically determined cm^2/gm	$K \times 10^3$		Experimental cm^2/gm	Graphically determined cm^2/gm	$K \times 10^3$
1.	0.5% Nicotine hydrogen tartrate + 0.5% Dhavda Gum	4.90	4.36	11.97	13.	4.34	3.89	18.30
2.	0.5% Nicotine hydrogen tartrate + 0.1% Dhavda Gum	—	—	broken	14.	3.95	—	broken
3.	0.5% Nicotine hydrogen tartrate + 0.5% Salai Gum	4.70	4.41	13.57	15.	5.28	4.67	9.16
4.	0.5% Nicotine hydrogen tartrate + 0.05% Saponin	9.57	7.67	9.47	16.	6.17	5.24	10.74
5.	0.5% Nicotine hydrogen tartrate + 0.02% Saponin	7.87	5.62	7.19	17.	5.55	4.95	10.61
6.	0.5% Nicotine hydrogen tartrate + 0.1% Gelatin	4.90	4.57	7.03	18.	4.57	4.16	5.32
7.	0.5% Nicotine hydrogen tartrate + 0.05% Gelatin	4.51	4.26	6.08	19.	4.18	3.93	5.21
8.	0.5% Nicotine hydrogen tartrate + 0.1% Sodium Lauryl Sulphate	9.86	7.67	10.17	20.	9.55	7.32	15.69
9.	0.5% Nicotine hydrogen tartrate + 0.05% Sodium Lauryl Sulphate	9.58	7.41	9.48	21.	6.13	—	broken
10.	0.5% Nicotine hydrogen tartrate + 0.1% Cetyl-trimethyl ammonium bromide	7.04	5.30	25.96	22.	5.83	5.55	17.60
11.	0.5% Nicotine hydrogen tartrate + 0.05% Cetyl-trimethyl ammonium bromide	3.97	3.75	21.26	23.	5.82	5.24	12.34
12.	0.5% Nicotine hydrogen tartrate + 0.6% Lecithin	3.73	3.23	0.15	24.	—	—	broken

Fig. 1. Distribution of Particle Sizes in Emulsions

- - First day - Emulsion No. 12
- - One week - Emulsion No. 12
- × - First day - Emulsion No. 1
- - First day - Emulsion No. 13

Nicotine-hydrogen-tartrate itself was not found to be a suitable emulsifying agent for kerosene/water or xylene/water systems. But when appropriate quantities of Indian gums and other adjuvants as listed in Table 1, were used along with nicotine-hydrogen tartrate stable emulsions were produced.

Size frequency analyses of kerosene emulsions stabilised by different agents reveal that saponin, sodium lauryl sulphate and cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide in combination with nicotine-hydrogen-tartrate produced very fine emulsions. Finest emulsions were produced with saponin as emulsifying agent as can be seen from the experimental initial specific area value 9.57 and also graphically determined initial specific area (Table 1 emulsion no. 4).

Dhavda and Salai gums, along with gelatin produced emulsions having initial specific areas 4.90, 4.70, 4.90, Lecithin produced very fine emulsion. In this case globule size distribution on the first day of preparation and after one week's storage time has been plotted in Fig. 1. It is evident from the size distribution curve that in this case the emulsion is very fine. It remains so even after storage of one week although there is change in the percentage of fine particles after storage. The other two cases (Emulsion no. 1 and 13) represent some what coarse emulsions as the no. of smaller particles has been decreased still further.

The stability coefficient values can be arranged in the following order:

CTMAB > Salai gum > Dhavda gum > SLS > Saponin > Gelatin > Lecithin.

Xylene emulsion, stabilised with sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS) had very fine globule distribution as is evident from the initial specific area value of 9.55. The order of fineness of the particle was found to be :

S L S > Saponin > CTMAB > Salai gum > Gelatin > Dhavda gum.

The graphically determined initial specific area also changed in the same order. With the change of internal phase the stability coefficient values were changed in the following order :

Dhavda gum > CTMAB > SLS > Saponin > Salai gum > Gelatin > Lecithin.

In general it can be concluded that CTMAB, Dhavda gum and saponin produced the most stable emulsions with all the systems. Salai gum also produced stable emulsions with kerosene oil as internal phase. Lecithin can not be recommended as a good emulsifying agent. Of course the internal phase plays an important role.

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